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Crop diversification and low-input farming across Europe: from practitioners' engagement and ecosystems services to increased revenues and value chain organisation

IDENTIFICATION OF THE OPTIMAL SOIL-CROP ASSOCIATION/AGRONOMIC PRACTICE PAIRS

Milestone MS18

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Executive summary

The milestone has the objective to provide an overview of the optimal soil-crop association/agronomic practice pairs among all those tested by the different partners in the Case Study (CS). The identification of the optimal pairs has been done in strict collaboration with the responsible of each CSs. To summarize the results and allow for a comprehensive evaluation, the same set of criteria was used for all the CSs, namely: yield (t/ha), gross margin (Euros/ha or Euros/tons), soil organic carbon (g/kg), and total nitrogen (g/kg) as exemplary of ecosystem services. With the aim to facilitate the reading of the document, the diversification is reported by country.

Evaluation of the diversified cropping systems showed that in many cases the introduction of new crops in rotation in arable land or intercropped as cover crops in permanent crops improved not only environmental aspects related to SOC and Total N concentration, but also economic aspects related to the gross margin.

In general, is important to find a trade-off between the environmental and economic factors by selecting the right crops to be used for diversification.

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1. Introduction

The milestone has the objective to provide an overview of the optimal soil-crop association/agronomic practice pairs among all those tested by the different partners in the Case Study (CS). The identification of the optimal pairs has been done in strict collaboration with the responsible of each CSs. In order to summarize the results and allow for a comprehensive evaluation, the same set of criteria was used for all the CSs, namely: yield (t/ha), gross margin (Euros/ha or Euros/tons), soil organic carbon (g/kg), and total nitrogen (g/kg) as exemplary of ecosystem services. With the aim to facilitate the reading of the document, the diversification is reported by country.

2. Identification of the optimal soil-crop association/agronomic practice pairs

Spain

Murcia region

CS1 - Almond intercropped with aromatic crops

In Case Study (CS) 1, two crop diversification strategies were tested compared to conventional system used as control:

crops are grown in between citrus tree rows.

- i) Conventional: Almond monocrop
- ii) Diversification 1: Almond intercropped with *Capparis spinosa* for food production
- iii) Diversification 2: Almond intercropped with *Thymus hyemalis* for oil production (November-March)

Table 1 - Agronomic, economic and soil data performances: differences between diversified and conventional cropping systems in CS1 in Murcia region (Spain)

Case study	Crop yield (t/ha)		Gross margin (Euro/ha)		Soil organic carbon (g/kg)		Soil total nitrogen (g/kg)	
	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control
CS1								
D1	0.09	0.16	-75.84	539.31	0.33	0.36	0.11	0.17
D2	0.02	0.16	-109.74		0.60	0.36	0.07	0.17

Identification of the optimal soil-crop association/agronomic practice pairs

The diversification with *Thymus hyemalis* gave better results than the diversification with *Capparis spinosa* in terms of agronomic benefits: better development and establishment of the intercropped plants and yield (Thyme essential oil production). The global environmental benefits of intercropping were, however, similar for both diversification practices. It is important to take in mind that the experimental blocks (although randomized selected at the beginning of the experiment) of the conventional monocrop systems had relatively better baseline edaphic conditions (e.g., greater soil organic carbon and nitrogen content) than the blocks where the crop diversification practices were implemented. Particularly, the diversification with *Thymus hyemalis* (D2) had lower TOC and Nt content (i.e., relatively worse baseline edaphic conditions) than the other treatments, and therefore more time will be needed to detect significant improvements in TOC and Nt when comparing with the conventional system. In terms of its financial performance, despite the differences shown in the table between the

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final and initial year, no significant differences were found between both diversification strategies and control monocrop regarding gross margin for the whole study period.

CS2 - Mandarin intercropped with herbaceous crops

In Murcia region, two types of diversifications have been applied in mandarin system. Diversification consists of intercropping as alley cropping; two to three crops are grown in between citrus tree rows.

- i) Conventional: Mandarin monocrop
- ii) Diversification 1: Mandarin with reduced tillage intercropped with vetch/barley and fava bean
- iii) Diversification 2: Mandarin with reduced tillage intercropped with vetch/barley and fava bean (2018), vetch/barley and purslane (2019), and vetch/barley and cowpea (2020)

The management practices applied are the following:

1. Addition of compost;
2. Green manure;
3. Integrated pest control;
4. Reduce tillage;
5. Cover crops (in the tree rows);
6. Regulated deficit irrigation.

CS16 - Intercropped melon

In Murcia region, two vegetable and legume monocrop were compared to the same crops intercropped with two different ratios. The fertilizer rate was reduced by 30% compared to monocrop. The tested treatments were:

Treatments:

- i) Conventional: Monoculture
- ii) Diversification 1: Row intercropping 1:1 (vegetable: legume crop)
- iii) Diversification 2: Row intercropping 2:1 (vegetable: legume crop)
- iv) Diversification 3: Mixed intercropping

Identification of the optimal soil-crop association/agronomic practice pairs

CS2 - Mandarin intercropped with herbaceous crops

Regarding **agronomic performance**, D1 strategy provided higher phosphorus content in soil, and higher number of bacteria of the genus *Pseudomonas*. In addition to this, fava bean crop from D1 strategy was more efficient **controlling erosion**, with decrease of erosion rates of more than 60%, while vetch/barley combination decreased erosion rates by a 40%. No clear effects could be revealed for Soil organic carbon (SOC) and total nitrogen (Ntot).

In terms of its **economic performance**, D1 strategy, which is mandarin intercropped with barley/vetch and fava bean, provides the best results, given the positive gross margin of fava bean as alley crop. Indeed, the gross

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margin results of D1 would improve if most of barley/vetch operations could be mechanized. In addition, gross margins for D1 show lower variability than those margins for monocrop between the first and last year. Besides the results shown, D2 provides even positive gross margin results in the second year, given the positive contribution of purslane. Hence, purslane could also be included as an alley crops to be intercropped in between mandarins.

Optimal pair: mandarine + intercropping of purslane

CS16 - Intercropped melon

Regarding agronomic performance, melon crop yield was higher when this one was intercropped with cowpea under MIX strategy. There were not significant differences between the kind of intercropping strategy in soil parameters or microbial community. However, soil parameters such as soil organic carbon, total nitrogen and phosphorus content showed higher values when the soil was cultivated with the intercropping systems than horticultural monocrop. In addition to this, higher number of bacteria of the genus *Pseudomonas* and new genera of bacteria were found in soils from intercropping systems than horticultural monocrop.

In terms of its financial performance, all intercropping strategies performance better than monocrop. Notwithstanding, MIX strategy is the one that provides the better gross margins, showing greater gains than the rest of intercropping strategies and monocrop in good financial years and mitigating losses in bad financial years. This is mainly motivated by the greater yields obtained in MIX strategy.

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Table 2 - Agronomic, economic and soil data performances: differences between diversified and conventional cropping systems in CS2 and CS16 in Murcia region (Spain)

Case study	Crop yield (t/ha)		Gross margin (Euro)		Soil organic carbon (g/kg)		Soil total nitrogen (g/kg)	
	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control
CS2	First year D1: mandarin (14.67) + fava bean (1.02) D2: mandarin (13.99) + fava bean (0.38) Last year D1: mandarin (11.42) + fava bean (2.69) D2: mandarin (7.68) + fava bean (1.24)	First year Monocrop: mandarin (20.92) Last year Monocrop: mandarin (11.97)	First year D1: 2,522.39 D2: -225.85 Last year D1: 1,257.56 D2: -1,354.06	First year Monocrop: 4,102.76 Last year Monocrop: 1,005.05	First year D1: 8.96 D2: 8.54 Last year D1: 8.50 D2: 6.19	First year Monocrop: 10.52 Last year Monocrop: 10.38	First year D1: 1.16 D2: 1.12 Last year D1: 1.09 D2: 0.96	First year Monocrop: 1.29 Last year Monocrop: 1.26
CS16	First year MIX: melon (26.27) + cowpea (0.10) 1/1: melon (20.28) + cowpea (0.87) 2/1: melon (24.76) + cowpea (0.46) Last year MIX: melon (10.84) + cowpea (0.16) 1/1: melon (9.64) + cowpea (0.44) 2/1: melon (10.60) + cowpea (0.29)	First year Monocrop: melon (15.1) Last year Monocrop: melon (8.56)	First year MIX: 4,539.24 1/1: 1,321.01 2/1: 3,376.39 Last year MIX: -2,310.11 1/1: -3,116.24 2/1: -2,490.83	First year Monocrop: - 1,337.99 Last year Monocrop: -4,268.91	First year MIX: 11.40 1/1: 11.70 2/1: 11.98 Last year MIX: 13.29 1/1: 12.18 2/1: 12.35	First year Monocrop: 9.81 Last year Monocrop: 11.11	First year MIX: 1.34 1/1: 1.28 2/1: 1.29 Last year MIX: 1.32 1/1: 1.29 2/1: 1.32	First year Monocrop: 1.12 Last year Monocrop: 1.19

Aragon region

CS3 – Irrigated and rainfed crops

Different diversification strategies are tested in Aragon (Spain) to analyse the impact of crop diversification (rotations and multiple cropping) and soil management managements (tillage, fertilization) on soil health compared to the conventional management practise, under both irrigated and rainfed conditions. Here, we focused on the main results observed in the case study under rainfed condition (CS3a – Rainfed barley). In CS3a, diversification strategies are compared to conventional system as follows:

- i) Conventional: Barley monocropping with CT
- ii) Diversification 1: Barley monocropping with NT
- iii) Diversification 2: Barley-wheat-pea rotation
- iv) Diversification 3: Barley-wheat-vetch rotation

Both crop rotations have a 3-yr duration and are based on three different crops in sequence

Identification of the optimal soil-crop association/agronomic practice pairs

The rotation with pea (barley-wheat-pea) gave the best agronomic and environmental results. Both rotations showed a positive difference in crop yields (compared with the monocropping system which showed a reduction in the difference in crop yields) but the yield difference of the rotation with pea was greater than the rotation with vetch. Furthermore, soil organic carbon showed a difference decrease in all the cropping systems tested in this case study. But the lower difference in soil organic carbon was observed in the barley-wheat-pea rotation. Economic performance did not present significant differences between the diversified systems and the monocropping.

Table 3 - Agronomic, economic and soil data performances: differences between diversified and conventional cropping systems in CS3a in Aragon region (Spain)

Case study	Crop yield (t/ha)		Gross margin (Euro/ton per year)		Soil organic carbon (g/kg)		Soil total nitrogen (g/kg)	
	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control
CS3a								
D2	0.285	-0.186	45.57	-13.89	-1.54	-1.57	0.12	0.15
D3	0.174	-0.186	6.42		-1.71	-1.57	0.21	0.15

Andalusia region

CS4 – Olive grove intercropped with annual crops

Different types of annual and perennial crops were grown as alley crops in olive yards in Andalusia, Spain, to observe the effect of intercropping compared to olive monocrop. The three diversifications are as follows:

- i) Diversification 1 (D1): Olive intercropped with *Crocus Sativus* for food production
- ii) Diversification 2 (D2): Olive intercropped with *Avena sativa* and *Vicia sativa* for food production
- iii) Diversification 3 (D3): Olive intercropped with *Lavandula x Intermedia* for oil production.

Identification of the optimal soil-crop association/agronomic practice pairs

The diversification with *Crocus Sativus* obtained better results than the diversification with *Avena Sativa* and diversification with *Lavandula* in terms of agronomic benefits: better development and establishment of the intercropped coverage and olive yield. Although it was difficult to establish a good development of diversifications and the *Crocus Sativus* cultivation implies a high investment for the farmer and a considerable risk of economic losses in case of possible agronomic problems (pests or drought) or crop failure. The implementation of diversification in olive orchards was significantly positive in the case of *Crocus Sativus* and *Avena Sativa* where increases in SOC and TN content were recorded with respect to monocrop (Table 3). However, *Lavandula x Intermedia* diversification did not increase the environmental values obtained in the control plots mainly due to the difficulty to establish an optimal development of the diversification and the cover crop in a highly degraded soil. Regarding to financial performance, both *Avena Sativa* and *Lavandula x Intermedia* showed negative values with significant differences compared to olive monocrop. However, *Crocus Sativus* gave positive values, although in the first year of cultivation there is no yield, indicating that this diversification could be the most profitable in economic terms if the final sale of *Crocus Sativus* bulbs is considered.

Table 4 - Agronomic, economic and soil data performances: differences between diversified and conventional cropping systems in CS4 in Andalusia region (Spain)

Case study	Crop yield (t/ha)		Gross margin (Euro/ha per year)		Soil organic carbon (g/kg)		Soil total nitrogen (g/kg)	
	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control
CS4								
D1	0.25	0.34	233	208	6.31	4.09	1.07	0.95
D2	0.19	0.34	-277	208	4.41	4.09	1.03	0.95
D3	0.19	0.34	-398	208	3.95	4.09	0.84	0.95

Italy

Po Valley region (Northern Italy)

CS5, CS6, and CS7 – Annual crop rotations

Italian case studies (CSs) were set-up in three real professional farms specialized in arable crops, i.e., tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) for industrial production in short rotation with cereals, such as irrigated maize (*Zea mais* L.) or rainfed durum or winter wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf. and *Triticum aestivum* L., respectively). The three farms, located in Po Valley region (Mediterranean North pedoclimatic region in Northern Italy), are associated with *Consorzio Casalasco del Pomodoro* (Casalasco Cooperative for industrial tomato production). The CSs 5 and 7 are in Lombardy Region (Mantua and Cremona provinces, respectively), while CS6 is in Emilia Romagna region (Piacenza province). In the Po Valley, the primary sector is more important than in other Italian regions due to the presence of many agri-food companies. In the area, there are highly specialized professional farms for cereals, horticulture, and livestock production. Current agricultural management practices are characterized by intensive production systems.

Three types of diversification strategies - oriented to farm resilience and ecosystem services - were introduced in the three CSs. The diversification strategies were planned to ensure technical and economic viability compared to the conventional intensive management practices. The conventional practices and the diversification strategies were as follows:

- i) Conventional: In CS5, 3-yr of maize in monocropping; in CS6, 3-yr of winter cereals in sequence (i.e., durum wheat, barley, durum wheat); in CS7 3-yr of tomato – durum wheat rotation (i.e., tomato, tomato, durum wheat). All the three CSs are characterized by uncovered soil period between crop cycles. This system was managed following a business as usual (BAU) management. In this system, farmers made decisions according to their market expectations as well as considering their structural and financial constraints.
- ii) Diversification 1: Introduction of a leguminous crop (i.e., pea for food) in the durum wheat-tomato rotation as new crop in rotation in order to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, increase carbon sequestration in soil, and improve the availability of soil nitrogen for the next crop. This crop was supported by technical external services.
- iii) Diversification 2: Introduction of tomato after pea harvest as multiple cropping.
- iv) Diversification 3: Application of digestate or pig slurry in combination with chemical fertilizers.

In all the CSs, the diversified crop rotation was durum wheat-industrial tomato-pea for food/industrial tomato as multiplecropping. The three field experiments were set-up to have all the crops in rotation each year. All the diversified systems were cultivated following the project research protocol and the harvested products were sold according to multi-year contract requirements.

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Table 5 - Agronomic, economic and soil data performances: differences between diversified and conventional cropping systems in CS5-7 in Po valley region (Norther Italy)

Case study	Crop yield (t/ha)		Gross margin (Euro/ha per year)		Soil organic carbon (g/kg)		Soil total nitrogen (g/kg)	
	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control
CS5	Wheat: 5.50; Tomato: 77.45; Pea: 3.47	Maize: 12.81	1455.67	1391.67	11.46	12.17	1.24	1.23
CS6	Wheat: 5.50; Tomato: 77.60; Pea: 3.48	Wheat: 4.40; Barley: 5.20	820.00	807.33	10.60	11.00	1.09	0.35
CS7	Wheat: 3.75; Tomato: 62.04; Pea: 4.31	Tomato: 28.69; Wheat: 5.07	-606.00	-176.67	9.36	9.64	1.18	1.21

Identification of the optimal soil-crop association/agronomic practice pairs

In CSs 6 and 7, the adoption of crop diversification strategies led to an increase in crop yield compared to the control over the 3 years. In CSs 5 and 6, the diversification strategies improved the gross margin compared to conventional system by 10% and 5%, respectively. Conversely, in CS7 gross margin under diversified system revealed a substantial negative difference compared to conventional scenario, as shown in Table 5. The negative results observed on CS7 was due to unpredictable negative conditions recorded during pea cultivation and tomato as double crop, especially in the first and second year of experiment. Therefore, in contrast to the initial expectations, in CS7 technical problems observed for growing these two crops in a short-term cycle negatively affected the gross margin results. Thus, to avoid this risk, a multi-year contract should be also included an insurance system for the multicropping system, similarly to what done for tomato. Moreover, farmer should be involved in additional activities in order to increase their competence and fill the knowledge gaps about the introduction of new crops and new crop management.

Regarding SOC and Total N, on average no significant differences between diversified and conventional systems were observed over the 3 years of experiment, except for Total N in CS6 (Table 5).

The Netherlands

Northern region

CS8 – Fodder crops

The diversification strategy consisted in cultivating maize (*Zea mays* L.) with bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) in different proportions, compared to the monocrop of maize. Between years there was the use of green manure: in 2018, Triticale + peas, in 2019 Soranigol, and in 2020 yellow mustard.

Table 4: Agronomic, economic and soil data: differences between diversified cropping systems in CS8 (The Netherland).

Table 6 - Agronomic, economic and soil data performances: differences between diversified and conventional cropping systems in CS8 in The Netherlands

Case study	Crop yield (t/ha)		Gross margin (Euro/ha per year)		Soil organic carbon (g/kg)		Soil total nitrogen (g/kg)	
	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control
CS8	27.33±8.04	26.67±6.93	2500	2500	26±4	25±3	2	2

Identification of the optimal soil-crop association/agronomic practice pairs

Maize with beans gives the best results for soil conditions, those reported on the table 4 are the average from 2020, but soil conditions and health (earthworms abundance) in 2019 were enhanced by the diversified crop.

Hungary

South Transdanubia region

In Hungary, horticulture and permanent crops were considered in two different case studies.

CS10 – Horticulture

This case study was located in Bács-Kiskun, Hungary, based on the growth of asparagus in sandy soils. In this area the conventional system is Asparagus monocropping. Diversification include Asparagus intercropped with *Pisum sativum* or with oat (*Avena sativa*).

Danube-Tisza Interfluve region

CS11 - Vineyard

The conventional system is Vineyard monocrop, the diversifications were:

- i) Diversification 1: Vine intercropped with yarrow (*Achillea millefolium*) for commercialisation.
- ii) Diversification 2: Vine intercropped with grass mixture as cover crop in interrow.

The effects of intercropping in vineyards were also studied in Baranya, Hungary, for three years.

Identification of the optimal soil-crop association/agronomic practice pairs

As shown in Table 7, the Asparagus/ pea (*Pisum sativum*) system, showed an increasing of SOC and nitrogen-forms, the improving soil structure, and showed a higher income. In the diversification with “asparagus+oat” the cover crop provides better covering against the wind erosion.

CS10 - Horticulture

In CS10 both intercrops provide some surplus income, with not very important difference among pea and oat, but the environmental impact is higher in case of diversification 2 with “Asparagus + *Pisum sativum*” related to the C and N values.

CS11 - Vineyard

In CS11, the vine combined with herb (yarrow) gives better result than the vine with grass (mixture) in interrow. The herb and herb-based products have higher value and provides higher income for farmers. Related to the soil C and N parameters the diversification 1 showed a slight increase of SOC.

Vine and interrow yarrow (*Achillea millefolium*) system improve soil structure and water budget, defending erosion, and gain higher income by the yarrow oil products. The diversification 2 (i.e., grass mixture as cover crop in interrow) is commonly used in organic farming, it has environmental importance, but no surplus income by this strategy.

Table 7 - Agronomic, economic and soil data performances: differences between diversified and conventional cropping systems in CS10 and CS11 in Hungary

Case study	Crop yield (t/ha)		Gross margin (Euro/ha per year)		Soil organic carbon (g/kg)		Soil total nitrogen (g/kg)	
	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control
CS10 Div2.	10.89 (asparagus) 1.93 (field pea)	11.510 (Asparagus)	12820 (asparagus) + 80 (field pea)	12820 (asparagus)	10.165	9.68	0.752	0.306
CS10 Div3.	10360 (asparagus) 1.77 (oat)	11.510 (asparagus)	12820 (asparagus) + 106 (oat)	12820 (asparagus)	9.78	9.68	0.317	0.306
CS11 Div2.	8.120 (grape) 1.006 (yarrow)	8.584 (grape)	75901 (wine) + 4321 (yarrow-oil)	75901 (wine)	23.515	20.39	1.215	1.165
CS11 Div3.	7.903 (grape) 0.936 (grass)	8.584 (grape)	75901 (wine) + - 89 (grass)	75901 (wine)	24.678	20.39	1.17	1.165

Finland

Southeast Finland region

In Finland, horticulture and permanent crops were considered in two different case studies.

CS12 – Cereal

Two diversification strategies were applied:

- i) Diversification 1: Cereal monocrop with annual autumn ploughing was diversified with no-till management. Diversification with no-till has been practiced during past 10 years, and before that plot has not been ploughed since 1991. Same crops have been cultivated in control plot which has been ploughed in each autumn when spring cereals were grown. Both plots have been fertilized with same amount of chemical fertilizers.
- ii) Diversification 2: The other diversification concerns interrupting the cereal monoculture with winter oilseed rape (ploughed plot and plot with no-till).

CS13/LT7 - Forage crop rotation

Four 4-year crop rotations have been practiced since 2001. Two crop rotations have been in forage production and two in cereal production. Crop rotation of both forage and cereal production have been diversified by growing legumes and following the principles of organic farming. In diversified forage crop rotation leys have been a mixture of timothy and clover while in control crop rotation they have been a mixture of timothy and meadow fescue. In the last year of the 4-year forage crop rotation, the diversified crop rotation has grown the mixture of vetch and oats while control crop rotation has grown barley for whole crop silage. Diversified forage crop rotation was fertilized with manure. In control forage crop rotation manure fertilization was supplemented by chemical fertilizers according to the limits of Agri Environmental Program.

Conventional cereal monoculture (CC) was diversified by one year timothy clover ley and green manuring. Diversified cereal crop rotation (OC) was fertilized with manure, in contrast to the control, which was fertilized only with chemical fertilizers.

Identification of the optimal soil-crop association/agronomic practice pairs

CS12 - Cereal

No-tillage implies appr. 20 % reduced yield of barley compared to conventional tillage. However, reduced costs, including also labour costs, due to no-till imply slightly higher gross margin (GM) B compared to conventional tillage. The difference is nevertheless rather small annually.

If accounting for pre-crop effects of oilseeds on spring cereals, reported by Peltonen-Sainio et al. (2019), introducing oilseeds in barley monocultures implies higher cereals yields at the following year after oilseed rape cultivation. Hence the average GM per a 5-year period is increased by €38/ha. This is a small economic gain, and it is dependent on the prices and yields of oilseeds which are both relatively volatile.

CS13/LT7 – Organic cereal crop rotation

Long-term organic cereal (OC) yields were 38% lower than conventional yields (CC). In forage production organic (OM) ley yields were 12% lower than conventional. TOC concentration of organic cereal crop rotation (OC) in 0-30 cm soil layer was higher than conventional control (CC), but difference was not statistically significant ($\alpha=0.05$) neither of the soil layers analyzed (0-10, 10-30 cm). Conventional forage crop rotation (CM) had higher TOC concentration than comparable organic crop rotation (OM), but difference was not statistically significant.

TN concentration in 0-30 cm soil layer was higher in organic cereal (OC) crop rotation than conventional farming

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(CC). Difference was statistically significant in 0-10 cm soil layer. TN was slightly higher in conventional forage crop rotation than organic farming.

If shifting from conventional dairy production and related forage grass cultivation to organic dairy production with related changes in forage grass production the GM B calculation shows a relatively significant €95/ha gain. This gain is however dependent on market process of organic dairy products and producer price of milk paid for a producer, and relatively less on the changes in grass forage cultivation practices. Adopting clover grasses to be used in conventional dairy milk production implies a small appr. €10/ha gain.

One may conclude that farm economy is not weakened because of the specific diversifications considered. There may be small economic gains because of diversifications. Hence farm economy seems not to be a barrier for the diversifications considered, but market demand of e.g. oilseeds and organic dairy products might be such barriers.

In Finland, the best diversification results with respect to soil quality were gained with having grass crops in the rotations as in CS13.

Table 8 - Agronomic, economic and soil data performances: differences between diversified and conventional cropping systems in CS12 and CS13 in Finland

Case study	Crop yield (t/ha)		Gross margin B (€/ha per year)		Soil organic carbon (g/kg)		Soil total nitrogen (g/kg)	
	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control	Diversified	Control
12	3070 (no-till)	3670 (conv. till)	271.3	210.6	22.5 0.585	25.2 -2.57	1.73 -0.126	1.84* -0.263
12	3866 (barley-barley-oilseed rape-barley)	3814 (barley, conv. till)	257.3	295.0	-0.8	-2.57	-0.26	-0.26
13	(OC, cereal) 2630	(CC, cereal) 4230	215.8	121.1	43.2	39.1	1.85	1.69
13	(OM, ley) 7390	(CM, ley) 8440	133.4	121.1	46.3	47.1	2.05	2.08

First row: concentrations based on 10-year results from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2021.105043>

Second row: 3-year results (not valid for comparing C changes to my opinion. CS13: concentrations based on 20-year results

Reference: Peltonen-Sainio P., Jauhiainen L., Honkavaara E., Wittke S., Karjalainen M. Puttonen E., 2019. Pre-crop Values From Satellite Images for Various Previous and Subsequent Crop Combinations. *Front. Plant Sci.* 10, 462. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2019.00462.

3. Conclusions

Based on results presented in the evaluation of diversified cropping systems, the introduction of new crops in rotation in arable land or intercropped as cover crops in permanent crops improved not only environmental aspects related to SOC and Total N concentration, but also economic aspects related to the gross margin.

Cover crops and rotation with leguminose increases SOC and favored a better nutrient supply. Diversification strategies showed variable ecological and economical benefits. In some case studies, not optimal results were observed in terms of marketable produces. However, the introduction of diversification strategies should achieve a balance between environmental and economic benefits such as those performed by optimal diversification strategy show in Table 9.

Table 9 – Summary of conventional and optimal crop diversification strategies per each Country

Country	Region	Conventional strategy	Optimal Diversification strategy
Spain	Andalucía	Olive monocrop	Olive intercropped with <i>Crocus Sativus</i> for food production
	Aragon	Rainfed barley monocrop	Rainfed barley-wheat-pea rotation
	Murcia	Almond monocrop	Almond intercropped with <i>Thymus hyemalis</i> for oil production
		Mandarine monocrop	Mandarine intercropped with purslane
		Melon monocrop	Melon intercropped with cowpea under MIX strategy
Italy	Po valley	Winter wheat and processing tomatoes	Introduction of multiple cropping i.e., pea for food/tomato for industrial production as double crop
		Maize monocrop	Introduction of multiple cropping i.e., pea for food/tomato for industrial production as double crop
The Netherlands	North region	Maize monocrop	Maize with beans
Hungary	South Transdanubia	Horticulture (Asparagus monocrop)	Asparagus intercropped with <i>Pisum sativum</i>
		Vineyard	Vineyard and interrow yarrow (<i>Achillea millefolium</i>) system
Finland	Southeast Finland	Cereal	Forage-cereal rotation